

Conductometric Study of Some Metal Complexes with Antipyrine

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Complexes of Hg^1 , Zn and Cd^2 , Fe^3 and UO_2^4 salts with Antipyrine (Ant.) have been studied gravimetrically. The conductometric titration of mixtures of Ant. with salts of five metals containing the stoichiometric amount of NH_4CNS with Zn, Fe and UO_2 salts and without it in case of Hg and Cd confirm the ratio in which they form complexes. Zn and Hg give white precipitate, Fe red and UO_2 yellow while Cd do not form precipitate. The salts $HgCl_2$, Zn $(CH_3COO)_2$, Cd $(NO_3)_2 \cdot 4H_2O$, $Fe_2(SO_4)_3 \cdot (NH_4)_2 SO_4 \cdot 24H_2O$, $UO_2(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ and NH_4CNS used were B.D.H. Analar quality and the reagent Antipyrine of Societe des Usines Chimiques (Rhône-Poulenc). Conductivity water (air free)

TABLE I

Job's method (Equimolar and Non equomolar)

Salts	$C \times 10^{-2}M$	P	Vol. at the peak ml.	Composition of the complex	Total vol. ml.
$UO_2(NO_3)_2$ and NH_4CNS	2.5	1	3	1 : 3	12
	2.0	1	3	1 : 3	12
	1.66	3	6	1 : 3	12
	2.50	2	4	1 : 3	12
	1.66	2	4	1 : 3	12
Fe(III) Alum and NH_4CNS	3.33	1	3	1 : 3	12
	2.22	1	3	1 : 3	12
	1.66	1	3	1 : 3	12
	1.66	2	4	1 : 3	12
	2.22	1.5	4	1 : 3	12
1.66	1.5	4	1 : 3	12	
$Zn(CH_3COO)_2$ and NH_4CNS	10.00	1	4	1 : 2	12
	6.66	1	4	1 : 2	12
	8.00	1	4	1 : 2	12
	6.66	1.5	4.5	1 : 2	12
	6.66	2	6	1 : 2	12
10.00	2	6	1 : 2	12	
$Cd(NO_3)_2$	10.00	1	4	1 : 2	12
	13.33	1	4	1 : 2	12
	20.00	1	4	1 : 2	12
	5.00	2	6	1 : 2	12
	20.00	0.66	3	1 : 2	12

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was used in the experiment and both the Job's method⁵ of continued variation and the monovariation method⁶ were adopted. The results are summarised in Tables I and II. In the tables, C represent the concentration of the metal solution and P the ratio C^1/C (C^1 being the concentration of Ant. Solution).

TABLE II

Monovariation Method (Direct and Reverse Titration)

Salts	$C \times 10^{-2}M$	$C \times 10^{-2}M$	Metal : Ant.
			at the inflection
HgCl ₂	10.00	10.00	1 : 1
	6.66	6.66	1 : 1
Cd(NO ₃) ₂	10.00	10.00	1 : 2
	20.00	20.00	1 : 2
Zn(CH ₃ COO) ₂	20.00	20.00	1 : 2
and	13.33	13.33	1 : 2
NH ₃ CNS	10.00	20.00	1 : 2
Fe(III)Alum	3.33	3.33	1 : 3
	2.22	2.22	1 : 3
NH ₂ CNS	1.66	3.33	1 : 3
UO(NO ₃) ₂	3.33	3.33	1 : 3
	2.00	2.00	1 : 3
NH ₄ CNS	3.33	10.00	1 : 3

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